

SOCIAL SCIENCES

INTERPRETATIVE APPROACH TO THE PRACTICE OF BODY MODIFICATIONS

Dirksen N.

Master's student

St. Petersburg State University

Saint Petersburg, Russia

Abstract

Despite the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the practice of body modification is of interest to an increasing number of people in Russia. The research problem is related to the contradiction between the growing popularity of body modifications, which has a favorable effect on the plastic surgery market, and the lack of knowledge of the motivations for plastic surgery and their consequences for the social life of individuals. In the interpretative approach, female corporality is understood as subjectively lived in the social world. On the basis of the reviewed studies of scientists, it was revealed that corporealities focused on an interpretive approach are focused on the micro-level of analysis - the bodily experience of women as full-fledged subjects of action, consciously making a choice in favor of working on the body.

Keywords: plastic surgery, interpretive approach, modification of corporality, motivation, patient's identity.

The coronavirus pandemic has contributed to the popularity of plastic surgery in society, international data confirm this fact. So in 2021, the American Society of Plastic Surgeons (ASPS) published a report stating that during the pandemic, 11% of women surveyed indicated that they are now more interested in cosmetic plastic surgery or non-surgical procedures than before the COVID-19 pandemic, and this the figure is even higher among women who have already had an operation or procedure at 24%. In addition, 35% of women who have had at least one previous cosmetic surgery or minimally invasive procedure plan to spend significantly or slightly more on treatment in 2021 than in 2020 [1].

According to the report of the International Society for Aesthetic Plastic Surgery (ISAPS), back in 2010 Russia ranked twelfth in the world in terms of cosmetic surgery [2]. Every year the popularity of body modifications in our country is growing. Thus, according to the report of the Vademecum Analytical Center, in 2017, 158,000 aesthetic plastic surgeries were performed in Russia, with a total profit of 12.3 billion rubles. According to the same report, in 2016 Russia ranked eleventh in the ranking of the leading countries in terms of plastic surgery [3]. In 2019, according to the report of the International Society of Plastic Surgery, 438 thousand plastic surgeries were already performed in Russia, which put it on the fourth line in the list of leading countries in aesthetic surgery. It is also noted that in the world the popularity of plastic surgery increased from 2015 to 2019 by 20.6% [4].

It should be noted that in our country the average cost of plastic surgery is still quite high compared to the average income of the population (for example, the average cost of nose plastic surgery (rhinoplasty) in St. Petersburg at the end of 2019 was 245 thousand rubles [5].

Despite the high cost and significant health risks, plastic surgery remains a desirable procedure for women around the world and the popularity of body modification is only growing. It should be noted that in the world there is an increase in the popularity of plastic

surgery among men. Thus, according to the Dubai Center for Cosmetic, Aesthetic and Reconstructive Surgery American Academy of Cosmetic Surgery Hospital, the ratio of women to men in 2013 was 82% to 18%, in 2014 the ratio changed to 77% and 23%, and in the first half of the year 2015 - 74% and 26% [6]. However, plastic surgery remains a predominantly female practice. For this reason, in our work, we limit ourselves to studying the significance of female body modifications only.

The practice of body modification, despite the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, is of interest to an increasing number of people in Russia. Thus, the *kommersant.ru* website claims that over the pre-pandemic four years, the volume of the plastic surgery market increased by 10%, reaching 7.5 billion rubles by 2020, and plastic surgeons in the capital noted a "rise in popularity" of appearance correction procedures against the backdrop of pandemic restrictions, it is associated with the so-called "zoom effect" - during video calls, people carefully studied their faces, and some refused to put up with what they saw [7].

The research problem is related to the contradiction between the growing popularity of body modifications, which has a favorable effect on the plastic surgery market, and the lack of knowledge of the motivations for plastic surgery and their consequences for the social life of individuals.

Subject of research: interaction of body modifications with the help of plastic surgery and the identity of patients.

Plastic surgery as an object of research today is a relatively new direction in sociology. It should be noted that it is directly related to the sociology of the body, which, as a separate discipline, began to form only in the 90s of the twentieth century. The sociology of the body originates at the end of the 20th century, in the work of Brian Turner «Body and Society», where a sociological theory of the body was proposed, in which the maintenance of the stability of the social system is made dependent on solving problems of managing people's bodies [8].

Let's consider the female corporality from the point of view of the interpretive approach.

So, L. Gaznyuk «Physicality as the basis of female identity in the culture of everyday life». The scientist draws attention to the fact that "beautification", that is, the desire to improve beauty, is associated with the assertion of a woman's own identity, and not with the influence of power structures on women's physicality. A woman, in this case, is seen as an active author of her life, and her decision about the need for surgical correction of her appearance is interpreted as a statement of a sense of self-worth, self-confidence and control over her life [9].

In his work, D. L. Gimlin writes: «I find it implausible that millions of women who engage in body work (body work) blindly submit to the control or choice to make their bodies physical manifestations (physical manifestations) of a subordinate position» [10, C34]. According to D. Gimlin, «women live above the system of gender oppression, they manage to create space for their own liberation within these very practices, which are often perceived as socially and personally destructive» [10, p. 37]. She notes that the processes at work in the structures designed to change the female body are more complex than many critics claim.

The author draws attention to the fact that the statements of some researchers about the pressure of a patriarchal society on women's bodily practices are rarely supported by empirical research: «While many writers and social researchers have argued that women face enormous pressure to conform to unfathomable ideals of beauty, only a few of these writers empirically studied how women personally explain their participation in the work on the body» [10, p.41].

According to Carla Rice, body modification is a conscious choice of patients in plastic surgery clinics. Subjecting their bodies to correction, women seek to find a "golden mean", which would primarily correspond to their sense of self [11].

As E. Giddens stated the essence of identity lies in the reflexivity of consciousness. This reflexivity of consciousness, according to Giddens, extends to corporality. The body, therefore, is the source of the individual's active involvement in everyday interactions, which are necessary to maintain a strong sense of one's own identity [12]. Bodily identity thus runs at the intersection of the individual and the social. Identity is what a person realizes through the expression «self-consciousness».

So, for example, S. Budgeon, describing the reasons for women's bodily modifications, says that girls primarily seek to increase self-confidence and change their usual behavioral strategies. Thus, in this case, the emphasis is on the personal choice of constructing a certain type of corporality based on the state of inner comfort and personal idea of ideality. In this sense, bodily practices are not seen as the result of the enslavement of women in a patriarchal society, but, on the contrary, as a result of the free choice of a woman who is able to make a decision consciously thanks to the success of the feminist movement in the 20th century [13].

Thus, sociological theories of corporality oriented towards an interpretative approach are focused on the micro-level of analysis - the corporal experience of women as full-fledged subjects of action, consciously making a choice in favor of working on the body.

In the interpretive approach, female corporality is understood as subjectively lived, which is mastered in the process of inclusion in the social world. In the research focus, focused on the female subject, it is important to explore the individual semantic load of the transformation of one's own corporality.

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